

**SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF BEHAVIOR
FORMATION IN ADOLESCENTS.**

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Abstract: Adolescence is a condition of special manifestation of psychological characteristics, in which certain changes occur as a result of extraordinary influences. This article talks about the socio-psychological factors of behavior formation in adolescence.

Key words: adolescence, behavior, group, interest, egocentric interests, deviant behavior, leader, character accentuation, delinquent behavior.

In particular, reactions of adolescent behavior are manifested in the interaction of environment and relatives as follows: 1. Emancipation reaction. This is seen in the desire to be free from the care, control and patronage of adults. The reaction is directed against the order, the rule established by adults. The need to "be free" is related to the desire for an independent life, and this reaction is more common in boys. 2. Group reaction with equals. There are two types of this: The first is based on one gender, in which the duties of the permanent leader and group members, their place in the group, are defined. In this group, the "adjutant of the leader" has no intellectual ability, but is physically strong, the "anti-leader" is the one who tries to take the place of the leader, the "hypocrite" is the one who moves both to and fro. will be teenagers. Such a group has its own territory, and strangers are not allowed to approach it. The composition of the group will be stable and new members will be accepted only on a trial basis. In the second type of group, the roles are not strictly distributed and there is no permanent leader. The duties of the leader are performed by various members of the group. The members of the group consist of representatives of both sexes and its composition is not stable.

3. Interest is a hobby reaction. Hobbies are important for adolescence. It has the following types:

1. Intellectual-aesthetic interests in subject matter, music, radio engineering, visual industry, literature.
2. Physical interests include actions to increase strength, endurance, and agility. is manifested in the effort to lead others.
4. Interest in collecting is seen in collecting different types of collections.
5. Egocentric interests. Striving to be the center of attention of others.
6. Passionate interest. Card game, gambling, risk taking.

7. Informational and communicative interest, seeking new information , random conversations and watching detective films, deviant behavior, which is considered a public phenomenon, is connected with economic, social, political and psychological processes occurring in society.

In some cases, processes in society are the cause of the appearance, expansion or disappearance of deviant behavior , while in others it can be a consequence. Deviant behavior is a violation of existing social norms in society. With each change of social norms, the opinion of the society changes dramatically: supporters and opponents of new views and forms of behavior appear, new norms replace the norms that are losing their influence. a hole appears. Deviant behavior is studied at two levels: individual and public. At the individual level, we are talking about a specific behavior of a certain person, at the public level, it is about a set of similar events, a system of violations of social norms. The status and degree of deviant behavior varies from country to country, region and territory. The structure and dynamics of the territory will be a qualitative indicator of deviant behavior. Structure means the relationship between all kinds of retreats, crime, other law violations, drunkenness, lack of spirituality, etc. within the existing territory . Transition from childhood to adolescence independence appears. Adolescent behavior is guided by his mind and relies more on personal experience. Behavior is formed differently from different views on social norms. Mechanisms of deviant behavior constitute a determination, motive, goal that acts contrary to the norm. Concrete types of deviant behavior: crime, alcoholism, suicide, drug addiction , etc. Constant family disagreements, dissatisfaction with the family and environment, misunderstandings in studies, among friends injure the adolescent psyche, or in this way encourage to change the existing situation. Practice shows that it is possible to achieve social reality even if sacrifice is made in any case. But, not realizing that a teenager can change his lifestyle, change his interests, cut ties with friends, get a profession , he considers this situation as an unavoidable situation and turns to indulgence, alcoholism, and drug addiction. puts on lipstick. If we simplify the mechanism of deviant behavior, it shows four main links : problematic (conflict) conditions, value-normative management, decision-making, implementation of the situation.

There are the following methods of psychological self-defense at the public and individual levels of deviant behavior :

1. Denial of reasons for liability.
2. Denial of damages.
3. Blame the accusers.

“Pre -spiritual consciousness” in the psychological defenses of deviant behavior . In the first lower level, there is no real moral vision, official prohibitions

are followed only because of punishments. In the second stage, a step is taken towards seeking to benefit from obedience to social norms. Therefore, at the pre-spiritual level of consciousness, personal benefits and interests are based on the subject's social vision. Character accentuation in adolescents. Bringing up the new generation, forming citizens who meet the demands of the society and help them fulfill their tasks has been the highest goal of every regime. The gradual improvement of the system of human personality formation in our republic is another clear proof of this opinion. Even during the former Soviet system, countless opinions were expressed and countless scientific and research works were carried out about the formation of appropriate ways of treating children at different age periods, and following the laws of their young psychological characteristics. The stated opinions do not doubt the scientific value of the conducted research, even if it is bitter, it must be admitted that the ideological demand of that time to form obedient and trustworthy members of society did not give full opportunity to apply these works in practice. Now the time has changed, the era has changed, the political, economic and social status of our Republic has changed. We have stepped on the path of integration. In the process of complex political and economic relations, there was a need for members of society who can take a clear direction, think independently, and express an independent attitude. In our republic, the process of forming the identity of citizens of a new society, who can meet these requirements on a large scale, has begun. "However, when making an objective assessment, we must admit that the measures we have implemented during the past period do not give the results that life demands today.

First of all, it should be noted that we still haven't completely gotten rid of the ideological views and prejudices of the old education system from the time of the Soviets. But among these periods there are periods of special importance, one of which is adolescence. In the scientific literature of this period, there are terms "transition period", "crisis period", "difficult period", all of which describe the characteristics of this period. It can be said that it reflects correctly. The main feature of adolescence is two developments: mental and physical, or in other words, it is characterized by the intensity of mental and somatic processes. Each of us in our children and foster children is characterized by the carelessness, 'polity, as obvious as excessive self-attention We have observed persistent, sharply manifested forms of behavior. During this period, it is possible to observe cases of rapid exhaustion, physical weakness, and susceptibility to various diseases. All these are considered psychosomatic changes and are considered the result of the interdependence of psychic and vasomatic processes. Most of the clearly manifested characteristics of a teenager are considered to be character traits that are visible in the system of his

relations. These peculiarities consist of a special appearance of the character, which is called "character accentuation" in psychology. has been extensively studied by many scientists.

Character accentuation - a character that represents a variant of the norm bordering on the psychopath is an extreme manifestation of certain qualities and sets of qualities. Character accentuation is distinguished by the fact that psychopaths do not have three characteristic features at the same time. These signs are: stability of character over time, generalization in all situations, and social maladaptation. In character accentuation, a person, like a psychopath, is not offended by all influences that cause psychological injury, but responds to some "sensitive" ones and ignores others. There are overt and hidden (latent) forms of character accentuation, and family upbringing characteristics, social environment, professional activity, physical health can easily overlap under the influence of important factors.

Character accentuation is formed during adolescence, smoothed and compensated over time. Acute affective reactions, neuroses, and even psychopathic development can become a reason for the formation of acute affective reactions in complex psychogenic situations that only affect the character's "empty bogoin" for a long time. Since character accentuation is bordering on psychopathic disorder types, its typology is based on the classification of psychopaths elaborated in psychiatry, but this classification also reflects the character traits of a mentally healthy person.

Based on different classifications, the following main types of character accentuation are distinguished: 1. Cycloid - alternating good and bad mood phases in different periods.

2. Hyperthymia - high mental activity with a constant high mood, a tendency to stick to several tasks at once and a thirst for activity, failure to complete the work started.

3. Labile - a sudden change in mood depending on the situation.

4. Asthenic - quickly tired, hot-tempered, prone to depression and hypochondria (depression - mental tightness, hypochondria - panic).

5. Sensitive - high sensitivity, narcissism, increased feeling of personal inadequacy.

6. Psychasthenic - high anxiety, suspiciousness, non-judgment, constant doubt and judgment, tendency to self-analysis, tendency to ritualistic actions and obsession.

manifested in separation from others, isolation, introversion, lack of empathy and difficulty in establishing emotional contacts emotional coldness, lack of intuition in the process of communication. 8.

Epileptoid - (sometimes with elements of cruelty) with the accumulation of aggression manifested in the form of tantrums and tantrums, a tendency to anger-sadness, quarrelsomeness, inflexibility of thinking, extreme pedantry (formalities).

9. Obsessed (parango'yal) - highly suspicious and disordered at the level of illness, persistence of negative effects, striving for superiority, high quarrelsomeness as a result of not accepting the opinions of others.

getting sick" when the need for recognition is not satisfied , is characterized by arrogance, engaging in dishonesty, lies, fantasizing and gloom, used to attract attention to oneself, sub' the tendency to suppress facts and events that are unpleasant for one.

11. Dysthymia - the predominance of a depressed mood, a tendency to depression, indulgence in the sad and sad aspects of life.

12. Unstable - a tendency to be easily influenced by others, always looking for new impressions, circles, easily establishing contacts of a superficial nature .

13. Conform - excessive dependence and submission to the opinions of others, lack of criticality and initiative, tendency to conservatism.

Character accentuation, as we mentioned above, is an indispensable sign of adolescence. every teenager, without exception, exhibits one or more of these characteristics. But in the next stages, these features should be smoothed out. Only in persistent psychogenic situations can these characteristics be strengthened. Such situations sometimes arise because of us adults, educators, parents . Sometimes, due to psychological illiteracy, because they do not know the laws of mental and somatic development, adults perceive such cases of teenagers as lack of education, deliberate indecency. Teachers with a negative "self-concept" generally aim to "control" children. As a result, the accentuation of the character becomes the reason for the subsequent transition to the psychopathic sphere . We adults, with our flexible personality traits, can easily adapt to children without mental strain. For this teenager, during the period of "personality", "sexual" formation, with our patience and kindness, we can help them to relieve mental tension, see ways to sublimate their natural sexual and aggressive tendencies. we can see.

Delinquent and criminal behavior is maintained through multilevel social processes. It will not be correct to focus only on individual problems of delinquent events and not to show the social causes of criminal behavior . According to Robert Merton, in today's consumerist society, most people pursue income, consumption, and success at all costs. For people who are denied, unrecognized, marginalized by society, it is very difficult to achieve these goals legally. Therefore, they try to achieve success by criminal means. Such people skimp, cheat, or steal, in short, they get by crime what they can get by law. At first glance, it can be concluded that such

people belong to the lower class of society. However, we should not forget the crime of the upper class of the society in the form of industrial criminalistics (buying, bribery, shortage), which is gaining momentum recently. Sometimes the habit of "sticking a label" in society also plays a big role in the fate of a criminal. A person commits a crime once and loses the opportunity to live without committing a criminal act. Delinquent carpera takes place in the following sequence: 1. Primary, random crime (delinquency) 2. Punishment. 3. Secondary delinquency. 4. More severe punishment. 5. More serious delinquent behavior. Thus, a delinquent person creates a closed circle that harms himself and others. Between the delinquent person and those who persecute him, a specific stereotype of relations is formed, in which one party demonstrates its power without regard for the person of the other victimized party. On the one hand, the ruling state institutions: the police, the prosecutor's office, the court, and their legitimacy is confirmed by democracy. On the other side, a delinquent person who is supposedly entitled to the share due to him. The process of "getting" is done either by robbery or indirect fraud, by means of a deficit. According to Paul Reywalpd, society, unimaginably, educates the criminals it wants to get rid of with its inexcusable actions and extremely severe punishments.

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